

BEHAVIOUR OF CHLORONITROBENZENES WITH HYDRAZINE
AND HYDRAZINE DERIVATIVES. PART VI. SOME
2-*p*-TOLYLNITRO-1:2:3-BENZOTRIAZOLES AND
THEIR 1-OXIDES

BY SHIAM SUNDER JOSHI AND SATYA PRAKASH GUPTA

A few phenyl-1:2:3-benzotriazoles and their 1-oxides have been obtained by condensation of halogen-nitrobenzenes and *p*-tolylhydrazine. Where formation of more than one product was possible, only one triazole derivative could be isolated. Structure to these compounds has also been assigned.

A simple method for the synthesis of 2-aryl-1:2:3-benzotriazoles (Witt. *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 2381) or the corresponding 1-*N*-oxides (Gaudinougin, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1907, ii, 76, 134; *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3822) is by the condensation of phenylhydrazines with reactive halogen compounds having a nitro group in their *ortho* position (Willgerodt and Ferko, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1888, ii, 37, 351). The first product of the reaction is a hydrazobenzene derivative (III) (Fischer, *Annalen*, 1878, 190, 132; Willgerodt *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1661; Werner *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3266) which in boiling acetic acid solution cyclises to a 2-phenyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole-1-oxide (IV) (Willgerodt, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1889, ii, 40, 253; Willgerodt and Ferko, *loc. cit.*; Giua, *Gazzetta*, 1918, 48, 11, 13) and in alcoholic solution the 1-oxide (IV) first formed is reduced to a 2-phenyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole (V) (Willgerodt and Ferko, *loc. cit.*; Walter, Dissertation, Freiburg, 18, 1889, S. 11; Sane and Joshi, this *Journal*, 1933, 10, 459).

During the present work, the behaviour of *p*-tolylhydrazine with a few reactive halogen compounds has been studied and as a result the preparation of some new 2-*p*-tolylnitro-1:2:3-benzotriazoles and their 1-oxides has been effected (Tables I and II).

TABLE I
2-p-Tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazoles.

Halogeno-nitrobenzene.	2-p-Tolyl-benzotriazole.	M. P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1-Chloro-2,4-dinitro-	6-Nitro-	167°	Yellow needles	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄	N: 21.87% C: 60.97	21.05% 61.42
1-Chloro-2:6-dinitro-	4-Nitro-	152°	Sepia needles	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄	N: 21.67	21.05
1-Chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-	4:6-Dinitro-	182°	Dark sepia	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₆	N: 23.09	23.41
1:2-Dichloro-4:6-dinitro-	4-Chloro-6-nitro	160°	Puff yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 12.10	12.30
1:3-Dichloro-4:6-dinitro-	5-Chloro-6-nitro-	199-201°	Dirty yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	C: 53.62 Cl: 11.98	54.07 12.30
1:4-Dichloro-2:6-dinitro-	6-Chloro-4-nitro-	207°	Light brown	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 11.04	12.30
1-Chloro-2:6-dinitro-4-methyl-	4-Nitro-6-methyl-	235°	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄	N: 20.52	20.90
1-Chloro-4:6-dinitro-3-methyl-	6-Nitro-5-methyl-	172°	Light yellow	"	N: 20.67	20.90
1-Chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-3-methyl-	4:6-Dinitro-7-methyl-	167°	Light brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₆	C: 62.55 N: 22.04	62.69 22.36
1:2-Dichloro-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	4-Chloro-6-nitro-7-methyl-	230°	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 11.54	11.74
2-Chloro-1-bromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	4-Chloro-5-nitro-7-methyl-	230°	Do	"	Cl: 11.43	11.74
1:2-Dibromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	4-bromo-6-nitro-7-methyl-	225°	Sepia prisms	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄ Br	Br: 22.87	23.06
1-Chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	4-Bromo-6-nitro-7-methyl-	225°	Do	"	Br: 22.78	23.06
1:4-Dichloro-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	6-Chloro-4-nitro-7-methyl-	210°	Sepia leaflets	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 11.53	11.74
4-Chloro-1-bromo-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	"	210°	Do	"	Cl: 11.59	11.74
1:4-Dibromo-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	6-Bromo-4-nitro-7-methyl-	182°	Dull yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄ Br	Br: 22.75	23.06
1-Chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	"	182°	Do	"	Br: 22.86	23.06
1:2:3-Trichloro-4:6-dinitro-	4:5-Dichloro-6-nitro-	192°	Light yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	Cl: 21.79	21.98
1:2:3-Tribromo-4:6-dinitro-	4:5-Dibromo-6-nitro-	300° (d)	Light brown	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂	Br: 38.67	38.84
1:2:5-Trichloro-4:6-dinitro-	4:7-Dichloro-6-nitro-	165°	Tan	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	Cl: 21.67	21.98
1-Bromo-2:5-dichloro-4:6-dinitro-	4:7-Dichloro-6-nitro	165°	Tan	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	Cl: 21.63	21.98
1:2:5-Tribromo-4:6-dinitro-	4:7-Dibromo-6-nitro-	222°	Faun leaflets	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂	Br: 38.47	38.84
1-Chloro-2:5-dibromo-4:6-dinitro-	4:7-Dibromo-6-nitro-	222°	Do	"	Br: 38.53	38.84
1:3-Dichloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-	5-Chloro-4-bromo-6-nitro-	179°	Dark sepia	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr	Cl & Br: 22.89	31.43 23.06
1:3-Dibromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-	5-Bromo-6-nitro-7-methyl-	> 330°	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄ Br	Br: 22.89	23.06
1:3:5-Dibromo-2:4:6-trinitro-5-methyl-	5-Bromo-4:6-dinitro-7-methyl-	295° (d)	Buff	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₆ Br	Br: 20.30	20.41

d = decomposition

TABLE II
 2-p-Tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazoles-1-oxides.

Halogeno-nitrobenzene.	2-p-Tolyl-benzotriazole-1-oxide.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1-Chloro-2:4-dinitro-	6-Nitro-	70%	170°	Yellow needles	$C_{13}H_{10}O_3N_4$	N: 20.58	20.74
1-Chloro-2:6-dinitro-	4-Nitro-	65	155°	Yellow	$C_{13}H_{10}O_3N_4$	N: 20.58	20.74
1:2-Dichloro-4:6-dinitro-	4-Chloro-6-nitro-	60	192°	Ruff	$C_{13}H_9O_3N_4Cl$	Cl: 11.62	11.66
1:3-Dichloro-4:6-dinitro-	5-Chloro-6-nitro-	78	196°	Turty yellow	$C_{13}H_9O_3N_4Cl$	Cl: 11.48	11.66
1:4-Dichloro-2:6-dinitro-	6-Chloro-4-nitro-	65	211°	Dark sepia	$C_{13}H_9O_3N_4Cl$	Cl: 11.53	11.66
1-Chloro-4:6-dinitro-3-methyl-	6-Nitro-5-methyl-	68	194°	Light yellow	$C_{14}H_{11}O_3N_4$	N: 19.70	19.72
1-Chloro-2:6-dinitro-4-methyl-	4-Nitro-6-methyl-	65	232°	Sepia	$C_{14}H_{11}O_3N_4$	N: 19.67	19.72
1-Chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-3-methyl-	4:6-Dinitro-7-methyl-	70	205°	Dark sepia	$C_{14}H_{11}O_3N_5$	N: 21.09	21.28
1:2:3-Trichloro-4:6-dinitro-	4:5-Dichloro-6-nitro-	75	190°	Light yellow	$C_{13}H_8O_3N_4Cl_3$	Cl: 20.79	20.94
1:2:3-Tribromo-4:6-dinitro-	4:5-Dibromo-6-nitro-	70	270°	Sepia	$C_{13}H_8O_3N_4Br_2$	Br: 37.06	37.38
1:2:5-Trichloro-4:6-dinitro-	4:7-Dichloro-6-nitro-	60	245°	Dark sepia	$C_{13}H_8O_3N_4Cl_3$	Cl: 20.73	20.94
1-Bromo-2:5-dichloro-4:6-dinitro-	4:7-Dichloro-6-nitro-	65	245°	Do	$C_{13}H_8O_3N_4Cl_3$	Cl: 20.65	20.94

Of the reactive halogen compounds investigated, 1-chloro-2:4:6-trinitro, 1:2-dichloro-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 2-chloro-1-bromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1-chloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1:2-dibromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1:4-dichloro-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 4-chloro-1-bromo-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1-chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1:4-dibromo-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1:2:5-tribromo-4:6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2:5-dibromo-4:6-dinitro-, 1:3-dichloro-2-bromo-4:6-dinitro-, 1:3-dibromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl- and 1:3-dibromo-2:4:6-trinitro-5-methyl-benzenes fail to furnish the corresponding 2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole-1-oxides.

Compounds that have only one nitro group in the *ortho* position to the reactive halogen atom can cyclise in one way when heated with *p*-tolylhydrazine, but when there are two nitro groups in both the *ortho* positions and the benzene ring is not symmetrically substituted, two products can be expected, according as the cyclisation takes place by interaction with one or the other of the two nitro groups. But it is noteworthy that in all such cases studied, only one compound could be isolated from the reaction product.

Structure to such compounds has been assigned on the basis of the known behaviour of reactive halogen compounds. Thus, the triazole, obtained by condensing *p*-tolylhydrazine with 1:4-dichloro-2:6-dinitro-5-methylbenzene (I: X=Cl; R₁=H; R₂=Cl; R₃=Me; R₄=NO₂), may be either 2-*p*-tolyl-6-chloro-4-nitro-5-methyl- (V: R₁=NO₂; R₂=Me; R₃=Cl; R₄=H; R₅=*p*-Tol) or 2-*p*-tolyl-6-chloro-4-nitro-7-methyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole (V: R₁=NO₂; R₂=H; R₃=Cl; R₄=Me; R₅=*p*-Tol). When the nitro group present in it is reduced and substituted by a chlorine atom by diazotisation and Gattermann's reaction, a dichloro-2-*p*-tolyl-benzotriazole is obtained. It was found to be identical by finding mixed melting point with 2-*p*-tolyl-4:6-dichloro-7-methyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole (V: R₁=R₃=Cl; R₂=H; R₄=Me; R₅=*p*-Tol) formed by a similar series of reactions from 2-*p*-tolyl-4-chloro-6-nitro-7-methyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole (V: R₁=Cl; R₂=H; R₃=NO₂; R₄=Me; R₅=*p*-Tol), a condensation product of 1:2-dichloro-4:6-dinitro-5-methylbenzene (I: X=R₄=Cl; R₁=Me; R₂=NO₂; R₃=H) and *p*-tolylhydrazine.

This is in agreement with the formation of 1-hydroxy-1:2:3-benzotriazoles (Joshi and Deorha, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 545) from substituted phenylhydrazines, where also the nitro group in *ortho* position to the methyl group is involved in the ring formation. Thus reactive halogen compounds: 1-chloro-2:4:6-trinitro-3-methyl-, 4-chloro-1-bromo-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1:4-dibromo-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl- or 1-chloro-4-bromo-2:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1:3-dibromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-, and 1:3-dibromo-2:4:6-trinitro-5-methyl-benzenes give 4:6-dinitro-7-methyl-, 6-chloro-4-nitro-7-methyl-, 6-bromo-4-nitro-7-methyl-, 5-bromo-6-nitro-7-methyl- and 5-bromo-4:6-dinitro-5-methyl-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazoles respectively.

By the condensation of 1:2:5-trichloro-4:6-dinitrobenzene (I: X=R₁=R₄=Cl; R₂=NO₂; R₃=H) with *p*-tolylhydrazine, three isomeric compounds, 2-*p*-tolyl-6:7-dichloro-4-nitro- (Va: R₁=NO₂; R₂=H; R₃=R₄=Cl; R₅=*p*-Tol), 2-*p*-tolyl-4:7-dichloro-6-nitro- (Vb: R₁=R₄=Cl; R₂=H; R₃=NO₂; R₅=*p*-Tol) and 2-*p*-tolyl-5:6

dichloro-4-nitro-1:2:3-benzotriazoles (Vc: $R_1 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_2 = R_3 = \text{Cl}$; $R_4 = \text{H}$; $R_5 = p\text{-Tol}$) could possibly result; but only one compound could, however, be isolated (Walter, Dissertation, Freiburg, iB, 1889, 3, 28). Identical compound, as found by the determination of the mixed melting point, is obtained by heating *p*-tolylhydrazine with 2:5-dichloro-1-bromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene (I: $X = \text{Br}$; $R_1 = R_4 = \text{Cl}$; $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_3 = \text{H}$) in alcoholic solution. Both of them must therefore be 4:7-dichloro-6-nitro-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole (Vb).

Similarly, 1:2:5-tribromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene (I: $X = R_1 = R_4 = \text{Br}$; $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_3 = \text{H}$) with *p*-tolylhydrazine gives 4:7-dibromo-6-nitro-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole (V: $R_1 = R_4 = \text{Br}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_5 = p\text{-Tol}$) which is identical with the product obtained from 1-chloro-2:5-dibromo-4:6-dinitrobenzene (I: $X = \text{Cl}$; $R_1 = R_4 = \text{Br}$; $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$; $R_3 = \text{H}$).

EXPERIMENTAL

2-*p*-Tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazoles were prepared by the action of *p*-tolylhydrazine on aromatic reactive halogen compounds (Method I) and also by the reduction of 2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole-1-oxides (Method II).

Method I.—A mixture of halogeno-nitrobenzene, *p*-tolylhydrazine hydrochloride and sodium acetate (1:2:2) in alcohol was heated on a water-bath. Soon after shining crystals began to separate. After about half an hour the liquid was cooled and filtered. The compounds separating were crystallised from toluene.

Method II.—2-*p*-Tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole-1-oxides were refluxed for about 2 hours either with alcohol or better with alcohol containing hydrazine hydrate. The product was cooled, filtered and the solids separating were crystallised from toluene. Identical derivatives, as found by their mixed melting points, have been obtained by both the methods and described in Table I.

2-*p*-Tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole-1-oxides were prepared by heating an acetic acid solution of the reactive halogen compounds and *p*-tolylhydrazine (1:2) on a water-bath for about half an hour. The mass was cooled and filtered. The solid so obtained was crystallised from toluene. These have been described in Table II.

4-Chloro-6-amino-7-methyl-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—4-Chloro-6-nitro-7-methyl-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole was dissolved in a boiling mixture* of equal quantities of alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid and then treated with an excess of zinc, added in small portions at a time. Boiling was continued till the liquid lost its colour. The mixture was filtered and alcohol evaporated off. An excess of sodium hydroxide solution was then added and the basic compound, set free, was extracted with benzene. On removing benzene and crystallising the residue from alcohol, light yellow crystals of 4-chloro-6-amino-7-methyl-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole were obtained, m. p. 237°. (Found: Cl, 12.76. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}$ requires Cl, 13.03%).

6-Chloro-4-amino-7-methyl-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—6-Chloro-4-nitro-7-methyl-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole on reduction by the method described above, gave 6-chloro-4-amino-7-methyl-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole, cream in colour, m. p. 247°. (Found: Cl, 12.63. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}$ requires Cl, 13.03%).

4:6-Dichloro-7-methyl-2-p-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole.—4-Chloro-6-amino-7-methyl-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole (2 g.) was dissolved in 40% acetic acid (25 c.c.), and HCl (conc., 8 c.c.) was added. The mixture was cooled (0°) and diazotised with a solution of sodium nitrite (2 g.) in water (12 c.c.) and filtered. The filtrate was treated with reduced copper (0.2 g.) and left overnight. The solid separating on crystallisation from benzene gave colorless crystals (1.4 g.), m.p. 167°. (Found: Cl, 23.80. $C_{14}H_{11}N_3Cl$, requires Cl, 24.31%).

Similarly, 6-chloro-4-amino-7-methyl-2-*p*-tolyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole on diazotisation and on application of Gattermann's reaction gave a colorless product, m.p. 167°, which was found to be identical with 4:6-dichloro-7-methyl-1:2:3-benzotriazole by mixed m.p.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
MEERUT COLLEGE, MEERUT.

Received September 18, 1957.